

Editor in Chief

**Dr Adebayo Ola
AFOLARANMI**

Department of Religious
and Intercultural Studies,
Lead City University,
Ibadan, Nigeria

Editors

**Assoc. Prof Adekunle
Olusola OTUNLA**

Department of Mass
Communication and Media
Technology,
Lead City University,
Ibadan, Nigeria

**Dr Michael
GBADEGESIN**

Department of Languages
and Literature
Lead City University,
Ibadan, Nigeria

Associate Editors

**Dr Emmanuel O.
MALOMO**

ECWA Gospel Centre,
Kano, Nigeria

**Rebecca Oluwatosin
BANJO**

Department of Peace
Studies and Conflicts
Resolution, Ajayi Crowther
University, Oyo, Nigeria

**Emmanuel Selome
FASINU**

Department of Political
Science, Wesley University,
Ondo, Nigeria

© 2025 Authors

**Predictive Role of Personality Traits on
Marital Duration among Couples in
Ibadan Baptist Conference, Oyo State,
Nigeria**

Emmanuel Adebayo DAIRO

*Department of Intercultural and Religious Studies,
Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria*
dairoemmy@gmail.com, +2348039612174

Victoria Folake IYANDA, PhD

*Department of Social Work, Lead City University,
Ibadan, Nigeria*
iyanda.victoria@lcu.edu.ng, +2348034097947

Abstract

Marital instability remains a pressing concern in many societies, including religious communities where strong values are traditionally upheld. Increasing cases of divorce, separation and emotional disconnection have become major concerns. This study therefore explores the predictive roles of personality traits on marital duration among couples within the Ibadan Baptist conference, Oyo state, Nigeria. It aims to identify psychological factors that contribute to enduring and satisfying marital relationships. A descriptive survey research design was adopted, using a quantitative approach. A total of 600 married individuals (300 couples) were selected through stratified random sampling across various Baptist congregations in Ibadan, employing multistage sampling procedure. Data were collected using validated instruments: the Big Five personality Inventory (BFI) to assess personality traits, and a marital duration scale to evaluate perceived relationship durability and satisfaction. Results from multiple regression analysis indicate that personality traits particularly, aggressiveness,

conscientiousness, and emotional stability significantly predict marital duration. The total personality score was positively and significantly associated with marital duration ($\beta = 0.894, p < 0.001$). These results indicate that the combined personality traits significantly predicted marital duration. It also shows a positive correlational investment tend to report more stable and satisfying marriages, likely due to shared values, community support, and faith-based coping mechanisms. The study concludes that a psychological compatibility relational plays crucial roles in sustaining durable marriages. It recommends integrating personality assessment into marital support programs within religious institution. These insights provide valuable implications for church leaders, marriage counselors, and policy makers seeking to strengthen marital relationships in faith-based settings.

Keywords: Personality Traits, Marital Duration, The Big Five Personality model, Ibadan Baptist Conference

Introduction

Marriage is an institution ordained by God. It supposed to be a lifetime agreement between a mature man and a woman to spend their entire life together for better or worse till death separates the duo (Animasahun, 2013). Marriage is the union of a man and a woman who makes a permanent and exclusive commitment to each other of the type that is naturally fulfilled by bearing and rearing children together, and renewed by acts that constitute the behavioural part of the process of reproduction (Girgis, 2012). Marriage is an established permanent relationship between a man and a woman, based on primary and secondary agreements and backed by legal injunctions, for companionship and procreation. It was further reiterated that it represents a lifelong commitment by two people based on contract and sanctioned by the state. It thus involves legal rights, responsibilities, and duties that are enforced by both secular and sacred laws. Most importantly, marriage is the basis for the institution of the family. Also, it is the process by which two people make their relationship public, official, and permanent. That is, the joining of two people in a bond that putatively lasts until death (Allport & Ross, 2021). Studies have shown that marriages provide unique benefits for a man, woman and the children from the marital union. It ensures accessibility of children to both mother and father whose joint efforts contribute significantly to their upbringing and development as the future member of the society (Folake, 2021).

Conceptual Framework

According to Caughlin (2022), the key factor widely acknowledged to impact marital relationships is personality traits. Personality traits refer to enduring patterns of thought, emotion, and behavior that influence how individuals interact with others. The big five Personality model comprising openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism provide a well-established framework for understanding personality. Also, all these can contribute to how individuals interact with their spouses handle conflict and manage daily stressors within marriage. Research has shown that certain traits, such as agreeableness, conscientiousness, and emotional stability, are associated with greater marital satisfaction, tolerance, and reduced conflict, all of which can contribute to longer-lasting marriages (Botwin et al, 2021). Personality could be seen as the most salient impression which an individual creates in others. It could be assessed by the effectiveness with which an individual is able to elicit positive reactions from others, under different situations (Atkins, 2019).

Several studies have linked self-reported openness, agreeableness and conscientiousness to marital outcomes found that decreases in spouse ratings of openness, agreeableness and conscientiousness were associated with decreases in marital satisfaction over the first two years of marriage. In their study of couples married an average of 18 years, reported that wives' openness, agreeableness and conscientiousness were each positively related to marital satisfaction. It was reported in their meta-analysis that agreeableness and conscientiousness are both associated with marital satisfaction, in that order. Others, however, have found no association between these traits and marital satisfaction (Atkins, 2019).

The associations between personality traits and marriage have been observed almost exclusively in studies with young adults; in contrast, comparatively little attention has been devoted to older adults whose marriages have withstood the test of time. Given that approximately half of all marriages end in divorce, and the median duration of marriages ending in divorce is eight years long-wed couples constitute a distinct subpopulation. In the brief review of studies published over 10 years in the *Journal of Family Psychology*, 183 articles examined marital dynamics, in which the average duration of the relationships was 9.43 years; only five articles examined normative relationship processes among couples married more than 20 years (Barelds, 2021)

Arowolo (2021) discovered that the dearth of studies pertaining to personality and marriage in long-wed couples constitutes a significant oversight in the literature. In their study, the traits of neuroticism and agreeableness were each related to global marital quality, and openness appears related to sexual satisfaction for women. Even in this study, however, the average age of spouses was less than 40 years at recruitment (SD $\frac{1}{4}$ 4.46). More problematic, marital satisfaction was assessed with only two items asking how happy and how dissatisfied participants were in their relationships.

The marital duration is known as longevity in marriage. It has been suggested in the literature as a factor that could affect how well a marriage works. Although there are no universal definitions for the size of a marriage, the number of years of marriage is not at all perplexing (Ofole, 2021). The studies indicate that marital duration or marital satisfaction may be positively or negatively correlated with religiosity and personality traits. This supports the well-known and undeniable fact that couples who have been married for longer are more mature and adaptable. It was contended that the marriage lifespan is fundamental since family length is one of the most important factors for family fulfillment. (Tabindi, 2021)

Marital duration is also known as the number of years spent together. The partners must be more adjusted the more extended the actual number of years they have been together (Ofole, 2021). Marital success is expected to be facilitated by the length of the relationship, given the adage that "experience is the instructor." (Tabindi, 2021). The following ten characteristics have been associated with a person's success throughout their marriage: dedication to intimate fidelity, aspiration to be a great parent, faith in God and religious commitment, the need to please and assist a spouse, being a good friend to a partner, and the willingness to forgive and be forgiven are all hallmarks of a lifetime commitment to marriage. Further, if a couple possesses all of these characteristics, they are more likely to remain married for a more extended period and achieve marital success, whereas if they do not, their likelihood of remaining married is reduced to half; consequently, the length of the marriage is dependent on other factors (Atkins, 2019)

According to Tabindi (2021), Marital success is measured by being in a high-quality, intact marriage, which is the first of all other marital outcomes. Success increases as we get older at marriages until the first to mid-twenties

and decreases after that. Marriage longevity is crucial because the length of a household is one of the many factors that can significantly impact family satisfaction. For a few theoretical reasons, divorces should be expected to decline naturally as partners get older and live longer together. Additionally, divorce or separation should have a higher cost for partners who have lived together for a long time because partners' tangible and intangible marriage-related investments can prevent them from getting divorced. Studies have addressed the obstruction to disintegration that is conjugal as more established age, significantly longer conjugal degree, the way that marriage is a lifetime commitment, and the presence of youngsters. The researchers hypothesized that marital quality declines over time and is more influenced by age than marital extent. (Belsky, et al, 2022) Changes in a person's perception of the other partner, especially after gathering negative information about the spouse after the marriage, lead to early separation or divorce. In contrast, those in short-term marriages cited personality differences and fundamental incompatibility as the primary reasons for their separation or divorce (Bouchard, et, al, 2019). However, changes in a couple's character, such as promiscuous or other life events, such as growing apart or lacking family cohesiveness, affect the couple's relationship. Given that the intimate partnership formed during a marriage is still essential to well-being, the persistence of the event makes sense. Whenever relationships are satisfying and stable, accomplices are better and live longer. Other pillars of health will also be at risk if the relationship fails. (Botwin, et, al, 2018)

Despite these known associations, limited research has explored how personality traits predict marital duration, especially within specific religious communities in Nigeria, most studies focus on marital satisfaction and stability but neglect the actual length of time couples remain married. Understanding the dynamics of personality in relation to marital duration is especially important in the Ibadan Baptist Conference, where spiritual guidance is often integrated with everyday marital decision-making.

This study, therefore, seeks to fill this gap by examining how personality traits predict marital duration among couples in the Ibadan Baptist Conference. The findings are expected to inform pastors, counselors, and Christian marriage educators about the psychological dimensions that contribute to lasting marriages, ultimately strengthening marital support systems within the church.

Statement of the Problem

However, in recent years, the increasing prevalence of marital breakdowns, separations, and divorce has raised concern, even within faith-based communities where high moral standards and spiritual values are emphasized. The increasing rates of divorce, separation, domestic violence and marital dissatisfaction have become a cause for concern for researchers, policymakers, and religious leaders (Bramlett, et al 2021). Despite consistent biblical teaching and church support structures at nurturing marital relationships, the challenge persists. Many couples struggle to maintain their marriages over time, suggesting that spiritual guidance alone may not be sufficient to ensure marital longevity. This has prompted a growing interest in identifying the psychological factors that influence how long marriages last. It is therefore important to explore the personality traits as psychological factors that contribute to how long marriages endure.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to examine the personality traits as predictors of marital duration among couples in Ibadan Baptist Conference, Oyo State Nigeria. Specific Objectives are to:

1. Examine the relationship between personality traits and marital duration among couples in Ibadan Baptist Conference
2. Determine the predictive joint effect of the personality traits and marital duration among couples in Ibadan Baptist Conference
3. Investigate the predictive relative effects of personality traits on marital duration among couples in Ibadan Baptist Conference

Research Question:

1. What is the relationship between personality traits and marital duration among couples in Ibadan Baptist Conference?
2. What is the predictive joint effect of personality traits on marital duration among couples in Ibadan Baptist Conference?
3. What are the predictive relative effects of personality traits on marital duration among couples in Ibadan Baptist Conference?

Significance of the Study

The findings of this study will help marriage and family counselors who are concerned with healthy relationship and marital stability and to be aware of predictive variables affecting marital stability. The knowledge will assist them in helping families with cases of marital conflict. This implies that the resolution of marital conflicts will be enhanced through the findings of this study.

Methodology

This research adopted descriptive survey research design. It is experimental research design. The research was used because it is appropriate for the testing of research questions. The population for this study comprised all the married couples in Ibadan Baptist Conference of the Nigerian Baptist Convention. Ibadan Baptist Conference is within the Ibadan metropolis. The sample for the study engaged 300 registered couples of the population (i.e., 600 participants) using multistage sampling procedure. At the first stage, purposive sampling technique is used to select Ibadan Baptist Conference as the study area. At the second stage, systematic random sampling technique was used to select 10 Associations out of the 20 Associations in the Conference within each stratum. At the third stage, simple random sampling technique was used to select 3 churches from each of the selected Associations totaling 30 churches in the Conference. At the last stage, 10 couples (i.e., 20 participants) were drawn from each of the 30 churches selected for the study.

Two standardized instruments were used; Revised Dyadic Adjustment Scale (RDAS) is a self-report measure that is used to assess couple marital relationships in terms of marital adjustment, quality, satisfaction and, marital stability. RDAS is a 14-item questionnaire adapted by Busby, Crane, Larson and Christensen (1995) and Personality Questionnaire was adapted from the Big Five Inventory (BFI) developed by John, Donahue and Kentle (1991) to measure the five personality factors/traits possessed by individuals based on five factor model of personality. The FBI is a self-report measure that contains 44 items or short statements that are easy to understand and fill within a short period of time.

Data collected from the questionnaire were carefully scored and analysed. Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) 21.0 versions was utilised for the analysis. Descriptive statistics including frequencies, percentages,

means, weighted means and standard deviations were used to analyse and to address the research questions raised from the study

Results

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between personality traits and marital duration among couples in Ibadan Baptist Conference?

Table 1 : Summary of Correlation between Personality Traits and Marital Duration

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Marital Duration	1.000						
Extraversio n	-.073	1.000					
Agreeablenes	.277*	.448*	1.000				
Conscientio usness	.157*	.102*	.694**	1.000			
Neuroticis m	-	-	-	-	1.000		
Openness	.246*	.273*	.675**	.712*	-	1.00	
Total Personality	.215*	.283*	.547**	.548*	.318*	0	
	.175*	.495*	.838**	.742*	-	.843	1.000
	*	*		*	.447*	**	
Mean	57.64	24.31	36.11	33.15	19.90	34.9	148.39000
Standard Deviation	50	50	83	33	67	000	
	6.548	3.422	6.687	6.538	5.399	5.94	14.74939
	32	76	72	69	99	156	

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). * Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

(Source: Researcher’s computation, 2025)

The Pearson’s correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between personality traits and marital duration among couples

in Ibadan Baptist Conference (Table 1). The results indicated that extraversion trait of personality was not significantly correlated with Marital Duration ($r = -0.073$, $p = 0.075$). However, it showed a significant relationship with Satisfaction ($r = 0.190$, $p = <0.05$) and Cohesion ($r = 0.282$, $p = <0.05$) dimensions of Marital Duration. Similarly, agreeableness showed a positive and statistically significant correlation with Consensus ($r = 0.393$, $p = <0.05$), Satisfaction ($r = 0.158$, $p = <0.05$), and Total Marital Duration ($r = 0.277$, $p < 0.05$), while Cohesion remains insignificantly related with it ($r = 0.065$, $p = >0.05$). Invariably, conscientiousness trait of personality was positively and significantly correlated with Consensus ($r = 0.261$, $p = <0.05$) and Total Marital Duration, yielding a correlation coefficient of 0.157 ($p < 0.05$), while Satisfaction ($r = -0.011$, $p = >0.05$), and Cohesion ($r = 0.073$, $p = >0.05$) were not statistically related with it.

In contrast, neuroticism trait of personality demonstrated a significant negative correlation with Consensus ($r = -0.310$, $p = <0.05$), Cohesion ($r = -0.170$, $p = <0.05$) and Total Marital Duration ($r = -0.246$, $p < 0.05$), while only Satisfaction dimension of Marital Duration ($r = -0.046$, $p = >0.05$) had insignificant correlation with it. Openness trait of Personality also had a positive and significant correlation with Consensus ($r = 0.358$, $p = <0.05$) and Total Marital Duration ($r = 0.215$, $p < 0.05$), while Satisfaction ($r = 0.035$, $p = >0.05$) and Cohesion ($r = 0.062$, $p = >0.05$) remain insignificantly correlated with it. When considering the Total Personality Score, the analysis revealed a positive and significant correlation between Total Personality Traits and Consensus ($r = 0.319$, $p = <0.05$), Satisfaction ($r = 0.107$, $p = <0.05$) and Total Marital Duration ($r = 0.175$, $p < 0.05$), but an insignificant relationship with Cohesion ($r = -0.041$, $p = >0.05$).

Therefore, these results prove that Total Personality and its Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, Openness and Neuroticism traits are significant correlates of Marital Duration, and could significantly predict it.

Research Question 2: What is the predictive joint effect of personality traits on marital duration of the study participants?

Table 2: Multiple Regression Analysis Result of Personality Traits on Marital Duration

Multiple R = .442
Multiple R² = .196
Adjusted R² = .189

Std Error of the Estimation = 5.89703

ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE

Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	5029.057	5	1005.811		
Residual	20656.328	594	34.775	28.923	.000
Total	25685.385	599			

(Source: Researcher's Computation, 2025)

A multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to examine the effect of personality traits on marital duration among couples in the Ibadan Baptist Conference. Judging from Table 2, the overall model was statistically significant ($F(5, 594) = 28.923, p < 0.001$). It yielded a multiple regression coefficient R of 0.442 ($R^2 = 0.196$), and Adjusted R^2 of 0.189, thereby indicating that approximately 18.9% of the variance in marital duration is accounted for by all the dimensions of personality traits combined.

Looking at the individual predictors, extraversion had a significant negative effect on marital duration ($\beta = -0.567, p < 0.001$). Conscientiousness also showed a significant negative relationship with marital duration ($\beta = -0.83, p < 0.001$). Neuroticism had a significant negative effect as well ($\beta = -0.631, p < 0.001$). Openness did not have a significant effect on marital duration ($\beta = -0.124, p = 0.133$). The total personality score was positively and significantly associated with marital duration ($\beta = 0.894, p < 0.001$). These results indicate that the combined personality traits significantly predicted marital duration. While certain traits such as extraversion, conscientiousness, and neuroticism negatively predicted marital duration, the overall personality composite had a positive relative effect on it.

However, agreeableness was automatically excluded by SPSS during the analysis which could be due to multicollinearity (two or more predictors in the model are highly correlated, making it difficult to isolate their individual effects on the dependent variable).

Therefore, these results show that total personality traits and its dimensions (extraversion, conscientiousness and neuroticism) are

significant joint predictors of marital duration. Also when taken individually, total personality trait was a significant positive predictor, while extraversion, conscientiousness and neuroticism were significant negative predictors.

Research Question 3: What are the predictive relative effects of personality traits on marital duration of the study participants?

Table 3: Multiple Regression Analysis Result of Relative Contributions of Personality Traits to the Prediction of Marital Duration of the Study Participants

Model	Un-standardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient		T	Sig.
	B	Std. Err	Beta			
(Constant)	72.701	3.74			19.390	.000
Extraversio n	-.688 .397	9 .086	-.360 .405		-8.049 6.343	.000 .000
Agreeablen ess	-.434 -.368	.063 .067	-.433 -.304		-6.493 -5.170	.000 .000
Conscientio usness	.260	.071	.236		4.897	.000
Neuroticis m		.053				
Openness						

(Source: Researcher’s Computation, 2025)

A multiple regression analysis was conducted to determine the relative contributions of personality traits to the prediction of marital duration among couples in the Ibadan Baptist Conference. Among the personality traits, Extraversion had a significant negative contribution to Marital Duration ($\beta = -0.788, p < 0.001$), Conscientiousness contributed negatively and significantly ($\beta = -0.477, p < 0.001$), Neuroticism had a significant negative contribution ($\beta = -0.5, p < 0.001$), Openness had an insignificant positive contribution ($\beta = 0.119, p < 0.131$)

Findings

The findings from the analysis, as shown in Table 1, 2 3, indicated a statistically significant indicating that the combined personality traits of talkativeness, tendency to find fault with others, reserved nature, relaxation under stress, forgiveness, and emotional stability significantly predict how often couples consider divorce or separation. This result is consistent with findings from previous studies that examine the role of personality in marital outcomes. For instance, in the previous studies it was highlighted that emotional and communicative traits are essential factors that influence marital stability and the likelihood of marital dissolution. Results from multiple regression analysis indicate that personality traits – particularly, aggressiveness, conscientiousness, and emotional stability – significantly predict marital durability, it also shows a positive correlational investment tend to report more stable and satisfying marriages, likely due to shared values, community support, and faith-based coping mechanisms

Conclusion

The findings from this study suggest that marital duration among couples in the Ibadan Baptist Conference is shaped by personality traits. The study confirms that personality traits, particularly talkativeness and reserved nature, significantly influence marital duration, with talkativeness being linked to fewer divorce discussions and more frequent quarrels, while reserved individuals tend to regret their marriages more often. The study concludes that a psychological compatibility relational plays crucial roles in sustaining durable marriages.

Recommendations

The following recommendations could be helped based on the findings of this study:

1. It recommends integrating personality assessment and faith-based into marital support programs within religious institution.
2. it is recommended that couples in the Ibadan Baptist Conference focus on enhancing communication and emotional expression within their relationships, particularly through joint activities and collaborative projects.

3. Since talkativeness and reserved nature were significant predictors of marital duration, couples could benefit from improving open dialogue and emotional intimacy.
4. Additionally, religious practices and engagement in shared spiritual activities could serve as a supportive mechanism for couples, particularly during times of conflict or marital distress.
5. Churches and religious organizations should consider offering counseling or workshops focused on relationship communication and conflict resolution, tailored to different personality types.
6. Furthermore, future studies should explore the role of other external factors such as socio-economic status and cultural practices in marital stability, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the dynamics at play.

References

- Aitken H. J, (2021) "*Measured intelligence, achievement, openness to experience, and creativity*". *Personality and Individual Differences Journal*. 36 (4):, 913–929
- Allport G RossJ, (2021). *Personal religious orientation and prejudice*. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 6(2), 43-44.
- Animasahun, R. (2015). Predictive Potentials of some psycho-socio- personal variables on divorce among Couples in Ibadan Nigeria. *Psychology*, 6,1711-1720. doi:10.4236/psych.2015.613167
- Arowolo D. O, (2021) *Correlates of marital stability among married couples in Ise-Oru Local Government Area of Ekiti State*. *The Counsellor Journal* 33 (1). 80
- Atkins D. C, (2019) *Using multilevel models to analyze couple and family treatment data: Basic and advanced issues*. *Journal of Family Psychology*, 19, 98-110.
- Barelds D. P. H, (2021) *Self and partner personality in intimate relationships*. *European Journal of Personality*, 19, 501-518
- Barelds D. P. H, (2021) *Self and partner personality in intimate relationships*. *European Journal of Personality*, 19, 501-518.
- Belsky J, & Hsieh K. H, (2022) *Patterns of marital change during the early childhood years: Parent personality, co-parenting, and division-of-labor correlates*. *Journal of Family Psychology*, 12, 511-528.
- Botwin M. D, Buss D. M, & Shackelford T. K, *Personality and mate preferences: Five factors in mate selection and marital satisfaction*. *Journal of Personality*, 65, 107-136. 2018

- Botwin M. D, Buss D. M, & Shackelford T. K, (2021), *Personality and mate preferences: Five factors in mate selection and marital satisfaction*. Journal of Personality, 65, 107-136
- Bouchard G, Lussier Y, & Sabourin S (2019). Personality and marital adjustment: Utility of the five-factor model of personality. Journal of Marriage and Family, 61, 651-660.
- Bramlett M. D. & Mosher W (2019). Cohabitation, marriage, divorce, and remarriage in the United States. National Center for Health Statistics. Vital Health Stat, vol 23. 20-23
- Caughlin J. P, Huston T. L, & Houts R. M,(2022), *How does personality matter in marriage? An examination of trait anxiety, interpersonal negativity, and marital satisfaction*.Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, 78, 326-336.
- Chen Z, Tanaka N,.Hiramura U, M, Shikai H,.Fujihara N,(2021),*The role of personalities in the marital adjustment of Japanese couples*. Social Behavior and Personality, 35, 561-572.
- Folake D,(2021),*Relationship between the big five personality factors and conflict management styles*.International Journal of Conflict Management. 9, (4), 336-354.
- Girgis, S. George, R. and Anderson, R. (2012). What is Marriage? Harvard journal of law and public policy, 34(1) 245-287 Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=1722155>
- John, O. P, Donahue, E. M., and Kentle, R. L. (1991). The Big Five Inventory-- Versions 4a and 54. Berkeley, CA: University of California, Berkeley, Institute of Personality and Social Research.
- Karaman, N. G., Dogan, T. and Coban, A. E. (2010). A study to adapt the big five inventory to Turkish. Procedia Social and Behavioural Science, 2, 2357-2359.
- Ofole, N.M, (2021), Determinant of Marital Satisfaction among young couples in Lagos State Nigeria : the Counsellor Journal, 34(1). 67
- Tabindi B.L (2021), The role of husbands and wives" emotional expressivity in the marital. Sex Roles Journal, 52, 577-587.